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Fabrication, Characterization, and Corrosion Protection of Hot Dip Aluminized Coatings for Steel Using Discarded Soda Cans

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ABSTRACT

Corrosion which seriously affects the quality and functionality of steel can be reduced by hot dip aluminizing which involves dipping substrate to a molten aluminum bath. Thus, this study aimed to produce hot dip aluminized coating for steel using discarded soda cans. A total of 80 steel nails with length of 65.62 ± 0.56 mm were used wherein 40 nails were intended for the hot dip aluminizing process at 650-700 °C with an average coating mass and thickness of 547 g/m² and 170 μm, respectively, with density of 2.627 g/cm³ following ASTM standards. Compared to the non-coated setups, the fabricated aluminum coating reduced 0.178g and 0.092g of corrosion products accumulation after immersions on H₂O₂ and NaCl solutions for 7 days and 4 weeks, respectively. Optical analysis of surface and cross sections of the coated samples showed less pitting, and corrosion products. Aluminum coating tends to pit that starts from small cracks and fractures when immersed in corrosive medium. Moreover, scanning electron microscopy showed that the coated nail sample experienced minimal corrosion in the form of thin cracks compared to non-coated nails which had relatively rough surface as result of heavy corrosion. In addition, t-test showed significant difference between the accumulated corrosion products' weights of coated and non-coated setups after immersing in NaCl ($t = -13.801$; $p = 0.000$) and H₂O₂ ($t = -31.005$; $p = 0.000$) wherein less corrosion product was obtained by the coated set-up ($\bar{x} = 0.036$ (H₂O₂) and $\bar{x} = 0.028$ (NaCl)). Thus, the results proved that the produced aluminized coating from waste soda cans provides a significant corrosion protection on the steel substrates.

Keywords: Corrosion, Aluminium coating, Solid waste management

1. INTRODUCTION

Corrosion greatly affects the performance, quality and physical properties of materials. On 2013, the global cost of industrial corrosion was about US\$1.5 trillion which consisted 1.95% of the global gross domestic product (Koch, et al., 2016). The corrosion rates of steel can be reduced by various methods such as reduction of the metal impurity content, use of coatings, application of cathodic protection, and addition of suitable alloying elements (ASM International, 2000, Hajar, Zulkifli, Mohd Sabri, & Wan Nik, 2016, Oguzie, Li, & Wang, 2004). Particularly, one of the most practical and economical method for protecting metals is through hot dip aluminizing.

Hot dip aluminizing involves dipping a material to a molten aluminum bath for a specific period of time. Hot dip aluminized products are commonly used in industries needing heat and oxidation resistance for steel (Awan, Ahmed, Ali, Shuja, & Hasan, 2008). These products are also known for their electrical conductivity and resistance from scaling, attractive corrosion, and sulfidation (Bahadur, & Mohanty, 1991).

According to Antonio (2010), the Philippines has an annual solid waste generation rate of about 10 million tons which translates to approximately 0.3 - 0.7 kg daily garbage for each Filipino. Much of this is determined in the urban areas where up to 44 percent of this waste is recyclable. Meanwhile, the Provincial Solid Waste Management Board of the province of Oriental Mindoro revealed a total of 40 tons of metal scraps solid wastes produced for the last two years wherein 47% of these wastes materials are cans and 40% of them are soda cans.

Table 1. Chemical Composition of Aluminum Soda Can
(Efunda, 2006, as cited in Al Saffar and Bdeir, 2008)

Aluminum Alloys	Weight of Elements		
	Al	Mg	Mn
3004	97.8	1.0	1.2
5182	95.2	4.5	0.35

Aluminum soda cans are generally made using two types of aluminum alloy presented on Table 1. They are mostly made of aluminum. Aluminum's basic properties do not change with physical processing and can be recycled repeatedly without loss of quality. It has a high strength-to-weight ratio, thermal and electric conductivity, corrosion resistance, malleability, elasticity and surface reflectivity. With various unique characteristics, aluminum can be used in different high quality and sustainable products (Aluminum Foundation, 2011). Thus, recycling aluminum soda cans offers some of the most pragmatic solutions to reduce the volume of generated waste.

In 1990 and 2009, the total aluminum production was estimated to be 28 million and 56 million tons. It is expected to increase to 97 million tons by 2020. Production of aluminum contributes to 1% of global annual greenhouse gas emissions, but through recycling of aluminum, the world can save 170 million tons of greenhouse gas emissions per year (Global Aluminum Recycling Committee, 2009). Therefore, recycling aluminum will not only help the environment by reducing solid waste and greenhouse gas emissions, it can be also be used to produce different materials such as anti-corrosion coatings.

In order to address problems in corrosion and solid waste, this study primarily aimed to produce hot dip aluminized coating for steel using discarded soda cans. Furthermore, this research sought to (i) describe the low-scale stove setup for making aluminum ingots and coatings, (ii) describe and characterize the aluminized coating based on optical analysis and scanning electron microscopy, and (iii) determine the corrosion protection of hot dip aluminized coatings against uniform and pitting corrosion based on the weight of corrosion products, optical analysis, and scanning electron microscopy. Furthermore, the researcher hypothesized no significant difference on the possible average weights of the corrosion products.

This research mainly focuses on the fabrication, characterization, and corrosion protection of aluminum coating from discarded soda cans. This promotes recycling of solid wastes like soda cans which could serve as great advantage in establishing greater corrosion protection for steel-based products, thus making safer and stronger building materials for constructions and infrastructures.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2. 1. Hot Dip Aluminizing

Discarded aluminium cans were collected, washed, and sun-dried. They were mechanically crushed using a hammer, reducing their surface area to lessen oxidation reaction that took place during the melting process.

Figure A. Charcoal Stove Setup as Alternative to Industrial Furnace

Current trends and methods in metal casting industry from “Advanced Melting Technologies: Energy Saving Concepts and Opportunities for the Metal Casting Industry” (BCS, Incorporated, 2005) were used as guide in making alternatives so that it can be done in a small scale. In the experimentation, an 18 mm steel basin was utilized as the crucible for melting the aluminum. It was pre-heated for 3 minutes until the outside of the crucible turned red. The cans were placed in the crucible one by one. Solid substances that formed on the top were removed. At temperature reaching 650-680⁰C based on TC-3200 digital thermometer and a type-K 8mm thermocouple probe, the aluminium was already metal and was transferred to a steel cup to form the ingots.

Nails were used as the test substrate for the experiments. One kilogram of 3-inch nails were purchased from a local hardware. Samples were obtained by cutting nails with length of 65.62 ± 0.56 mm. The metal cleaning was done according to ASTM G1 (1999). The nails were immediately coated after the cleaning.

For the coating process, the ingots were melted in the cup. The nail samples were hot-dip in the aluminium bath. After 15 seconds, the nail samples were removed from the crucible and were let to cool down.

2. 2. 1. Characterization of Coating

To quantify the coatings’ average mass, the weight of the nails were recorded before and after the coating process. The mass of each coating was computed according to a formula by ASTM A 428/A 428M (2006) presented below:

$$C = [(W_1 - W_2) / A] \times N$$

where C = mass (g/m²) of coating, W₁ = mass (g) of coated specimen, W₂ = mass (g) of bare specimen, A = area (mm²) of coated specimen, and N = constant (1×10^6).

The coatings’ estimated thickness was also computed using the conversion factor $1 \text{ g/m}^2 = 25.4 \text{ } \mu\text{m}$, involving type 2 aluminum coatings, as stated in ASTM A 463/A 463M (2002). Cylindrical ingots were made by letting molten bath to cool in a metal cup to serve as the mold. Density was calculated by measuring the mass and volume of the three different-sized samples.

2. 2. 2. Surface Morphology by Digital HD Microscope and SEM

A portable digital microscope with 1000x magnification was used to further analyse the surface and cross sectional morphology of the specimens after hot dip aluminizing.

For the surface morphology of the coated specimens compared to the non-coated, a scanning electron microscopy was conducted using Hitachi TM3000 table top microscope to describe the surface morphology of the coated and uncoated specimen immersed in NaCl solution for 2 weeks.

The specimens were cut into 5 mm using hand saw. They were placed in the specimen holder of the apparatus. Air was released. Different magnifications were utilized to obtain micrographs that were taken using a laptop computer. On the other hand, a Digital HD microscope with 1000x magnification was also used for the generation of different optical macro shots and analytical imaging of the surface structure of the specimens (coated and non-coated) in two set-ups.

Figure B. Scanning Electron Microscopy using Hitachi TM3000

2. 2. 3. XRF-Chemical Composition Analysis

Figure C. XRF Test Using Olympus INNOV-X Pro

A handheld Olympus INNOV-X Pro was used for XRF (X-Ray fluorescence) chemical composition analysis. A fabricated ingot from the discarded soda cans were used as the test subject. The measurement window was placed against the ingot. The trigger was pulled for about 90 seconds until the X-Ray warning light stopped blinking. Then, the results were exported to a laptop.

2. 3. Immersion Test

The corrosion protection of the aluminum coating was determined by computing the weight of accumulated corrosion products on samples. Eighty setups were prepared, 40 specimens of coated nail samples and another 40 of non-coated nail samples. The corrosion

testing procedures were done according to ASTM G 31 (2004) wherein the setups were immersed separately in closed test tube setups containing 5% sodium chloride solution and 3% hydrogen peroxide for 4 weeks and 7 days, respectively. The NaCl solution was prepared following the ASTM 85 (2011) in which 50 g NaCl and enough distilled water were mixed to formulate 1000 mL of artificial saltwater. The weight of the corrosion products were computed by adding the amount of decrease in weight in the specimen after mechanical brushing and the weight of the accumulated corrosion products in the test tubes after the solutions were removed by evaporation method through the use of gas lamp.

Figure D. Immersion of Coated and Non-Coated Specimens in Corrosive Media

2. 4. Pitting Behaviour

The cross section and surface morphology of the coated and uncoated specimens after 4 weeks of immersion in NaCl solution were analysed using a digital microscope to observe their pitting behaviour. Methods were guided by ASTM G 46 (2005). Pitting densities and shapes in different regions were recorded using the “standard rating chart for pits” and “variations in the cross-sectional shape of pits” chart provided in ASTM.

2. 5. Risk and Safety

For the safety of the researcher throughout the experimentations, protective gloves, masks, and eye protections were used in handling chemicals. Safety protection clothing such as visor, apron, gloves, and boots were also used in melting the soda cans. Proper ventilation on the room was observed. The acids were disposed after neutralizing the solution. Other chemicals such as sodium chloride and hydrogen peroxide solutions were buried underground.

2. 6. Statistical Analysis

Data were presented as the mean \pm standard error of the mean (SEM). T-test was used to statistically analyze quantitative data.

3. RESULTS

3. 1. The physical properties of the fabricated aluminum coating and the result of hot dip aluminizing using the simple stove setup are shown in Table 2.

Table 2. Characteristics of Aluminum Coating and Process; ^a n = 60, ^b n = 3

Coating Method	Hot dip aluminizing
Product to Cans Ratio	3.95 g/can
Recycling Efficiency	30%
Coating Mass	$546.78 \pm 36.66 \text{ g/m}^2$ ^a
Coating Thickness	$170.219. \pm 11.41 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ ^a
Density	$2.627 \pm 0.01 \text{ g/cm}^3$ ^b

The Table 2 presents the characteristics of produced aluminum coatings. Computations using a formula by ASTM A 428/A 428M showed that the average mass of coating of 60 samples is $546.78 \pm 36.66 \text{ g/m}^2$. The lowest and highest obtained mass were 87.90 g/m^2 and 1282.31 g/m^2 , respectively. Coatings' estimated thickness was also calculated based from the average mass of 60 samples according to ASTM A 463/A 463M. The average estimated thickness was $170.219. \pm 11.41 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$. The lowest and highest obtained estimated thickness were $27.36 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and $399.19 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, respectively. On the other hand, the created metal ingots obtained an average density of $2.627 \pm 0.01 \text{ g/cm}^3$. The recycling efficiency was computed to be 30%, wherein a can produced 3.95 g of Al product.

3. 2. The surface morphology of the aluminized coating according to HD digital imaging showed different appearance such as shiny, smooth and rough morphology.

Figure 1. Optical shots of the surface morphology of coated specimens with 1000x magnification

Optical shots of the surface of coated specimens after hot dip aluminizing were taken as shown in figure above. In Fig. 1A, a shiny smooth appearance can be seen. A non-shiny appearance was shown in Fig. 1B. On the other hand, Fig. 1C shows a rough morphology with random bumps.

3. 3. The aluminized coating increased weight consistently during the first 10 hours of immersion and maintained a weight without significant change after.

Figure 2. Mean Weight Gain Percentage of 20 Coated Specimens during 24 Hours of Exposure to NaCl Solution

The changes in the mean weight percentage of 20 coated specimens during 24 hours exposure to NaCl solution can be seen at Fig. 2. It can be observed that there was a rapid weight gain percentage of 5.05 % in the specimens after 9 hours of exposure. This may be due to coatings' absorption of water. As immersion time increases, there is no much change in the weight of the specimens.

3. 4. The aluminized coating increased weight consistently during the first 10 hours of immersion and maintained a weight that doesn't significantly change after.

Table 3 above shows the results of handheld XRF composition analysis of the aluminum ingot produced from the discarded soda cans. The test revealed that the fabricated metal was composed of 95.33 % aluminum and 1.46 % magnesium. There are also traces of Si, Mn, Fe, Zu, Zn, Cr, and Ni. On the other hand, very small amount of Ti and V was detected in only one replicate.

Table 3. Chemical Composition According to XRF Test
* n = 3; ** detected in only one replicate

Composition	Percentage ($\bar{x} \pm \text{SEM}$)*
Al	95.333 \pm 0.425
Mg	1.461 \pm 0.500
Si	0.772 \pm 0.400
Mn	0.532 \pm 0.244
Fe	0.334 \pm 0.169
Cu	0.099 \pm 0.047
Zn	0.746 \pm 0.697
Cr	0.442 \pm 0.419
Ni	0.257 \pm 0.251
Ti**	0.028
V**	0.013

3. 5. There was more corrosion products on the non-coated specimens after immersions in sodium chloride and hydrogen peroxide solution.

Figure 3. Coated and Non-Coated Specimens after Exposure to NaCl (4 weeks, top) and H₂O₂ (7 days, bottom) Solution

The photographs on Figure 3 show the accumulation of corrosion products in coated and non-coated specimens after 4 weeks immersion in NaCl solution and 7 days immersion in H₂O₂. It can be seen that there is accumulation of brownish, reddish, and blackish substances on non-coated specimens while whitish substances were formed on coated specimens.

Figure 4. Mean Weight of Accumulated Corrosion Products on Coated and Non-Coated Specimens after Exposure to NaCl (4 weeks) and H₂O₂ (7 days) Solution; * indicates significance at 0.05

Figure 4 shows the mean weight of accumulated corrosion products on 40 coated and 40 non-coated specimens after exposure to corrosive media. Corrosion products with weight of 0.213 g and 0.120 g were collected in non-coated nails immersed in H₂O₂ and NaCl solution, respectively. On the other hand, only 0.036 g and 0.028 g were gathered from the coated specimens.

It shows that there is much more corrosion product accumulation in the non-coated specimens compared to the coated materials. It indicates the corrosion protection that the aluminized coating provides. It can also be noticed that there is more corrosion product accumulation in hydrogen peroxide solutions than in the sodium chloride solution. This indicates that corrosion testing can be accelerated by hydrogen peroxide solution.

T-test revealed that there is significant difference between the weights of accumulated corrosion products in the coated and non-coated specimens in NaCl ($t = -13.801$; $p = 0.000$) and H₂O₂ ($t = -31.005$; $p = 0.000$) solutions at 5% level of confidence. Thus, it can be stated that the aluminized coating has significant corrosion protection for steel against rusting in NaCl and H₂O₂ media

3. 6. Based on scanning electron microscopy of the specimens after 14 days of immersion in NaCl solution, the non-coated nail had very rough and damaged surface, while the coated specimen showed rod-shape particles and have very minimal signs of corrosion such as cracks.

Figure 5. SEM micrographs with different magnification x60, x500, x1500, x3000 (A, B, C, D) of non-coated nails after immersion in the NaCl solution for 2 weeks

The scanning electron microscopy in Figure 5 and 6 shows the surface morphology of a non-coated and coated nail after immersion for 2 weeks.

A rough random morphology with the presence of bumps can be observed with the non-coated nails. Meanwhile, only thin minimal cracks and smooth continuous fractures were present in the coated nails.

Figures 5D and 6D displayed the closest shot of the non-coated and coated nails respectively given at x3000 magnification. Based from Fig. 5C, pits, cracks, and random rock-like formations were the corrosion products that can be seen on the non-coated nails. Whereas, in fig. 6B smooth needle-type or rod-like structure with different sizes were the

dominant corrosion products featured in the surface of coated nails. Minimal fractures and cracks were also observed on fig. 6D.

Figure 6. SEM micrographs with different magnification x60, x500, x1500, x3000 (A, B, C, D) of coated nails after immersion in the NaCl solution for 2 weeks

3. 7. Based on digital HD imaging of non-coated specimens during immersion in hydrogen peroxide solution, the non-coated nails developed red-brownish rust and blackish rust after 1 hour and 29 hours, respectively.

The figure above shows the optical shots of non-coated nails' surface during immersion in 3% H₂O₂ for different time. Before the immersion (fig. 7A), the nails had uniform and clean appearance. After the specimens were immersed, brown-reddish rust formed rapidly as seen in fig. 7B. The solution with non-coated nails turned brownish, while the solution with coated nails remained clear. After 6 hours (fig. 7C), bigger black spots formed on the surface. Light reddish bubble-like substances formed on the surface (fig. 7D) after 14 hours. However, these substances settled down on bottom when the nails were moved. Eventually, black rust

formed on non-coated nails after 29 hours (Fig. 7E). These black substances were tightly attached to the nails. The nails had the same black substances until the 7 days immersion.

Figure 7. Optical shots of surface morphologies of non-coated nails during immersion in 3% H₂O₂ solution for a) 0 hour, b) 1 hour, c) 6 hours, d) 14 hours, and e) 29 hours

3. 8. Based on digital HD imaging of coated specimens during immersion in hydrogen peroxide solution, the coated nails consumed longer time before a specific region in the steel substrate was exposed to corrosive medium and develops rust.

Figure 8. Optical shots of surface morphologies of coated nails during immersion in 3% H₂O₂ solution for a) 0 hour, b) 1 hour, c) 6 hours, d) 14 hours, e) 29 hours, f) 50 hours, g) 75 hours, h) 98 hours, i) 122 hours, j) 147 hours, and k) 162 hours

The figure above shows the optical shots of the development of pitting on specific region on coated nails' surface during immersion in 3% H₂O₂ at different time intervals. On Fig. 8A, the clean surface of the aluminum coating was observed. After 14 hours of

immersion (Figs. 8B, 8C, 8D), soft whitish substances formed near cracks and fractures that formed. A small pitting appeared after a 29-hour exposure (fig. 8E). On fig.8F, two pits can be seen that were connected by a crack. This particular crack on the small region eventually lead to bigger pits as immersion time increased on figs. 8H, 8I, 8J, and 8K.

3. 9. The aluminum coating exhibited different pitting behavior such as sizes, shapes, and densities as shown in figure 9. The coated nails suffered minimal to moderate corrosion.

Figure 9. Optical Shots of Cleaned Coated Specimens After Immersion in NaCl Solution for 4 Weeks

The figure above shows the optical shots of cleaned coated specimens after immersion in NaCl solution for 4 weeks. Different morphologies with different levels of pitting were observed from the 20 setups. Shots displayed on top showed minimal corrosion on aluminum coatings. Morphology with no sign of corrosion has been observed (Fig. 9A). Minimal cracks, fractures, and small pits were observed on Figs. 9B, 9C, and 9D. Figures 9E and 9F displayed multiple small pits with cracks and fractures. On the other hand, a section with multiple small

pits or high pitting density was observed on Fig. 9G. Figure 9H displayed multiple big pitting. A pitting density rating of 1,2,3,4 and 5 were seen in different parts of the coated samples.

3. 10. The non-coated specimens exhibited different pitting behavior such as sizes, shapes, and densities as shown in figure 9. The non-coated nails suffered minimal to heavy corrosion.

Figure 10. Optical Shots of Cleaned Non-Coated Specimens After Immersion in NaCl Solution for 4 Weeks

Figure 10 above shows the cleaned, non-coated specimens' surface morphologies after immersion in NaCl solution for 4 weeks. Different kinds of pits were observed. Figure 10A and 10B showed long shallow pits. Long pits were noticed on Fig. 10C that seemed to be deeper. On the other hand, Figs. 10D and 10E showed multiple pits sections that had a very high pitting density. A pitting density rating of 1,2,3,4 and 5 were seen in different parts of the non-coated samples.

3. 11. The cross sections of non-coated specimens suffered from pitting corrosion after immersion in sodium chloride for 4 weeks as shown in Figure 11.

Figure 11 shows the cross-sectional morphology of non-coated nails after immersion on NaCl solution for 4 weeks. Figure 11A showed the overall appearance of the cross section. Figures 11B, 11C, 11D, and 11E showed a more detailed structure wherein pitting can be observed. Shallow and deeper pits can be perceived on Figs. 11B and 11D, respectively. On the other hand, pitting with irregular shapes can be noticed on Figs. 11C and 11E. Narrow-deep, elliptical, wide-shallow, subsurface, and undercutting shaped pits were observed. Most have vertical microstructural orientations.

Figure 11. Cross-Sectional Morphology of Non-Coated Nails After Immersion on NaCl Solution for 4 weeks

3. 12. The cross sections of coated specimens suffered from minimal pitting corrosion after immersion in sodium chloride for 4 weeks as shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12. Cross-Sectional Morphology of Coated Nails After Immersion on NaCl Solution for 4 weeks

The optical shots of the cross sectional morphologies of coated specimens after 4 weeks of immersion in NaCl solution can be seen at the figure above. The overall cross section morphology was presented in fig. 12A. More detailed shots were presented on figs. 12B, 12C, 12D, and 12E. Very minimal pitting can be noticed. This was due to the coating protection of

the aluminum layer, wherein it got damaged first before the substrate. Elliptical, wide-shallow, and undercutting shapes of pits in the aluminized layer were observed.

3. 13. When the coating was removed from the aluminized nails after immersion in sodium chloride solution for 4 weeks, a shiny structure was observed. Some parts also portrayed damaged in the shiny structure, while some don't have shiny structure.

Figure 13. Optical Shots of 3 Different Surfaces of Immersed Nails After Removing Coating with 1000x Magnification

Figure 13 shows the optical shots of three different surfaces of immersed nails after removing coating with 1000x magnification. It can be gleaned on Fig. 13A that the nails had a shiny structure with no pitting while Fig. 13C displayed signs of minimal corrosion and pitting. On the other hand, nails also had parts that were significantly shiny with signs of corrosion as shown in Fig. 13B.

Most of the nails were observed having a shiny appearance. The parts of pitting in the coated nail also showed pitting on the nail's surface.

4. DISCUSSION

In making of the product, hot-dip aluminizing was utilized since it involved the use of crucible and stove that are easily accessible. Choosing a good crucible was vital to the success of melting the cans, since the process involved a low-scale production. An empty fire extinguisher container was first tested as it was commonly used in metal foundries due its durability and thickness. But due to these conditions, the available stove setup could not provide enough heat to melt the aluminum. The use of thinner steel cans as crucible lead to melting of the steel cans themselves, but due to its thinness, crucible failure happened. Finally, a steel basin was used that had a thickness that can absorb enough heat to melt the cans and can withstand melting process for several cycles. The ideal recommended dipping time for the samples used was 15 seconds. Going beyond 15 seconds produced a thick non-uniform coating, while less than 15 seconds exposure to molten bath was not enough for the coat to spread uniformly and only few parts have retained the coating. This process produced 3.95 g per can which only resulted to 30% recycling efficiency.

This low percentage can be further increased by using higher temperature in melting the cans or using a quality furnace. With a simple setup, most of the cans comprised the non-melted impurity that was removed in the melting process.

Based on the experimentations, the aluminized coating aided corrosion protection for steel against rusting. This corrosion protection of the aluminum coating was possibly due to the formation of a non-uniform, thin and non-coherent layer of aluminum oxide Al_2O_3 that provided a shield for the substrate. However due to exposure from chloride ions, the oxide film can be damaged at certain parts that leads to pits formation on the coating's surface (Ezuber, El-Houd, & El-Shawesh, 2008). This leads to less corrosion products compared to the non-coated specimens after immersions in corrosive media.

A factor that contributes more corrosion in the coated samples is the coating's uneven and rough structure. The random bumps and other surface defects in the surface of aluminum coating were shown in HD digital imaging. This leads to a higher surface area being exposed to corrosive media that contributes to higher corrosion rate (Yue, & Cao, 2015). The higher surface area is also associated in the coating's water absorption as signified by the immediate weight gain in the samples after immersions.

After several research reviews, it can be stated that the surface SEM micrographs of the aluminum coating was different compared to several aluminum products. Some surface morphology featured multiple rock-like structures, continuous straight lines, multiple dots on surface, and smooth morphology (Maulidin, & Kimapong, 2015, Meng, Dong, Zhou, Liu, & Yin, 2017, Bidin, Abdullah, Shaharin, Alwafi, Riban, & Yasin, 2013, Yue, Lu, Zhu, Zhang, & Zhang, 2009).

According to one study that described rod-shaped products in the form of FeAl, the needles or rod-shaped structures were the result of phase transformation of Fe_2Al_5 that was associated with aluminum consumption during the oxidation (Chang, Cheng, & Wang, 2009). Another study featured a few rod-shaped with multiple circular structures of $TiAl_3$ particles (Ding, Xia, & Zhao, 2014). However, these studies don't relate the structure of rod-shaped structure on how the substrate can be protected. Thus, a deeper analysis is needed to characterize the surface morphology of the fabricated aluminum coating and how the structure functions.

Another characteristic of aluminum when coupled with other metals is its tendency to pit as it was immersed in corrosive environment. This is common to aluminum products since corrosion protection is mostly based on the surface film that forms on corrosive environments. When the protective film deteriorates, aluminum becomes susceptible to pitting that can be seen in cross sectional morphologies of the samples (Jafarzadeh, Shahrabi, Hadavi, & Hosseini, 2009).

Moreover, the formation of pits, cracks and rock-like structures as seen in the optical shots and scanning electron microscopy of the unprotected nails can also be attributed to the aggressive chloride ions (El Maghraby, 2010). Pits illustrated in the generated optical microshots of coated samples after immersion can only be seen in almost 95% of the surface. This means that the aluminum coating still provides a physical barrier on most parts of the steel substrate even after immersion in artificial saltwater after 4 weeks.

After a thick layer of the aluminum coating was removed through mechanical means, a thin rough, shiny, and metallic layer was observed in between the outer aluminum and the steel substrate.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Based on the results and discussion of the current investigation, aluminum coating performs an explicit effect on preventing the corrosion of the steel nail samples.

Samples of coated and non-coated nail show definite differences on their surfaces via scanning electron microscopy and HD digital imaging. The coated nail samples significantly experienced minimal corrosion in the form of thin cracks. Non-coated nail samples, however, had big random bumps as the result of a heavy corrosion.

The study was able to show significant difference on the accumulated corrosion products weight for the coated and uncoated steel specimens having greater obtained t-values of -13.801 and -31.005 to $p = 0.000$ for H_2O_2 and NaCl set-ups respectively wherein greater amount of corrosion products (in g) was produced by the uncoated specimen. Therefore, aluminized coatings from discarded soda cans affirmed its capacity in providing corrosion protection for steel.

This project suggests the use of discarded soda cans in big-scale metal foundries and industries for production. The appearance and consistency of the coating can be further improve. Electrochemical characterizations can be done to analyze the fabricated metals properties.

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